

Stratification of responses to tDCS intervention in a healthy paediatric population based on resting-state EEG profiles

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ABSTRACT

Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) is a non-invasive neuromodulation technique with a wide variety of clinical and research applications. As increasingly acknowledged, its effectiveness is subject dependent, which may lead to timely and costly treatments with ineffective results. We propose the usage of electroencephalography (EEG) for the analysis and prediction of individual responses to tDCS.

We have analysed resting-state EEG activity within a clinical trial for the development of paediatric treatments based on tDCS to identify subgroups of participants with an homogeneous electrophysiological profile. Cognitive behavioural tasks were used to assess the impact of the intervention afterwards. We have implemented an unsupervised learning approach to stratify participants based on their resting-state EEG spectral features before the tDCS intervention. We have then applied a correlational analysis to identify EEG profiles associated with tDCS subject behavioral response to the specific stimulation.

In the results we found specific digital electrophysiological profiles that can be associated to a positive response, whereas subjects with other profiles respond negatively or do not respond to the intervention. Findings suggest that unsupervised machine learning can be successfully used to interpret and eventually predict responses of individuals to tDCS treatment.

Keywords: tDCS, EEG, ADHD, ASD, healthy, IDLPFC, rIFG, cognitive behavioural tasks, treatment, prediction.

Introduction

In recent years, Non Invasive Brain Stimulation (NIBS) techniques and, in particular, transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS)^{1,2} have been successfully used to study brain function, treat mental disorders and enhance cognitive functions in adults. This therapy can be applied as an effective treatment option^{3,4}, which is particularly interesting in the absence of alternative interventions. Its application in paediatric populations however has been limited due to initial concerns⁵. In children, stimulation parameters cannot be directly translated from studies in adult populations since electric fields generated in the brain during stimulation are affected by anatomical differences such as brain volume, skull thickness, white matter - gray matter ratio and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) volume⁶.

Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is one of the most prevalent neurodevelopmental chronic conditions which affects 5.9% of youth and 2.5% of adults (South America, North America, Europe, Australia, Asia, the Middle East and Scandinavia)⁷. Electroencephalography (EEG) has been used to characterize the ADHD population. The use of EEG-based markers overcomes some limitations of classical subjective assessments based on interviews and physical examinations. Existing reports on EEG biomarkers mention increased theta band power and decreased beta band power in the frontocentral brain region^{8,9}, phase-amplitude coupling (beta-gamma) deficits in the frontal-left hemisphere¹⁰, and modified peak alpha frequency¹¹ among others.

Given the concerns that drug-based treatments of ADHD have raised in the past, there is an ongoing search for treatments with reduced or no side-effects¹². Current drug based treatments and behavioural therapy in ADHD are also challenged by the different phenotypes and related symptoms of the pathology, as well as the complexity associated to the developing brain¹³. TDCS intervention for ADHD constitutes an interesting alternative to drug treatments¹⁴. However, an important factor to take into account in the development of efficient tDCS interventions is the inter-subject variability of the tDCS effect^{15,16}. Here, machine learning techniques can be of help to identify differentially responding subgroups based on clustering of behavioural responses during tDCS interventions¹⁵. Moreover, other works have implemented unsupervised methods to characterize responses to different treatments based on clustering of genetic¹⁷, clinical¹⁸ and functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging¹⁹ data. These works report patient subgroups within a priori uniform group of patients. We propose to use EEG data for such a patient stratification. Previous work using EEG data report prediction of response to treatment by means of Machine Learning (ML) approaches^{20,21}. Variability in response to TMS and tDCS interventions in patients suffering from depression or anxiety can be also explained by individual differences in baseline EEG activity^{22,23}. EEG is an attractive modality for clinical application due to its lower cost and faster application time than other neuroimaging modalities. In the present study, we have developed and applied an unsupervised clustering method to EEG data to extract so called digital phenotypes²⁴. Therefore, EEG is used for the first time to stratify tDCS response in a healthy paediatric population.

As an exploratory stage in preparation of the main clinical trial, a tDCS intervention in a healthy paediatric population has been designed to target 2 areas of interest, namely the left Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (IDLpFC) and the right Inferior Frontal Gyrus (rIFG). TDCS is applied for each area of interest both while the participants are concurrently performing a task and without any concurrent task during the stimulation. Resting state EEG was acquired before and after the tDCS intervention. We present a methodology for healthy participants stratification based on their resting state profile of EEG activity before treatment and their behavioural responses to the tDCS intervention. Behavioural metrics correspond to Accuracy and Reaction Times of Flanker task, N-Back task and Continuous Performance Task (CPT). In order to determine baseline EEG profiles, we extract spectral features, which are relevant features in paediatric EEG studies²⁵ and in particular ADHD^{8,26}. Relative band power is calculated - this measure is preferred over the absolute band power to normalize absolute differences among participants that may present abnormalities in their anatomy²⁷. To stratify participants we use the clustering algorithms Spectral Clustering, which has good results for non-convex data²⁸, and Fuzzy Clustering, which is of interest since it can be applied to data in which boundaries are ambiguous and contain outliers²⁹. A correlational analysis is then applied between the membership of participants to each of the a-priori electrophysiologically homogeneous groups and the a-posteriori behavioural results. Significant correlations of a particular cluster group is tested against the rest of the groups in order to confirm responders. The methodology and results we describe in this article contribute to the understanding of the variability of tDCS treatment response, with a particular focus on the specific scenarios in which the treatment is effective. We support the relationship between the tDCS response and the EEG profile on the fact that both depend on bioelectrical characteristics of the brain. Hence EEG features act as a proxy of these biophysical characteristics.

Interestingly, positive responder groups correspond to participants with a non-typical brain profile, presenting either a slowing of the EEG or a spread of increased alpha rhythm over frontal areas. This methodology can be applied later to stratify patient treatment (specifically, tDCS) enabling to focus on the specific digital phenotypes in which treatment is more probable to become effective. Personalization of treatment, applying tDCS only to groups of patients predicted to have positive results, would save costs, time and engagement to the treatment rates.

Materials and methods

Participants

Data come from a healthy population taking part in a clinical trial for the development of treatments for Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) based on tDCS. The study was approved by the local ethics committee of the Medical Faculty at Kiel University, Germany, and was carried out in accordance with the latest revision of the Declaration of Helsinki and registered in the German Trial Register with number DRKS00008207.

A total of N=56 children aged 10 to 17 years (32 females, mean age: 14.09 years, SD: 2.1) were recruited in the Medical Faculty at Kiel University. Informed consent from the participants and their parents was obtained before the experiment. Exclusion criteria consisted of substance or medication consumption, implants and devices in the body, pregnancy, birth before pregnancy week 37, birth weight lower than 2500 grams, IQ score lower than 80 assessed with CFT 20-R Test (Culture Fair Intelligence Test)³⁰, neurological and psychiatric disorders (past or present), brain surgery, presence of epilepsy in the participant or family in the present or in the past, social and health impairments as assessed with CBL (Child Behavior Checklist)³¹, FBB ADHS (Fremdbeurteilungsbogen für Aufmerksamkeitsdefizit Hyperaktivitätsstörungen)³² and SRS (Social Responsiveness Scale)³³. All participants' characteristics can be found in Tables 2 and 3 of the Supplementary Information.

Experimental Protocol

Experimental Design

A randomized, sham-controlled, double-blind, crossover study design was implemented. Participants came for 6 experimental sessions (see Figure 1). The first 2 sessions (T1-T2) correspond to participants screening and an optional fMRI scan. Participants then came back 4 times to receive the tDCS interventions (T3-T6) which were of 4 different types, administered in a randomized order: active tDCS with a concurrent task, active tDCS with a non-concurrent task, sham tDCS with a concurrent task and sham tDCS with a non-concurrent task. There was a minimum washout period of 7 days in-between sessions. At the start of each stimulation session, participants were asked to complete an assessment of their current mood, motivation, and any adverse event since the last session. Following the stimulation session, participants completed a questionnaire on the safety, tolerability and blinding of the stimulation.

Figure 1. Experimental Design. Each participant is assessed at 6 time points, T1 corresponds to an EEG screening, T2 to the optional fMRI, and T3-T6 to the randomized interventions (offline/online, tDCS/sham).

Participants were randomly divided into 2 groups: participants in Group A were stimulated in the left Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (IDLPFC) and performed the N-Back Task in the concurrent task condition, whereas participants in Group B were stimulated in the right Inferior Frontal Gyrus (rIFG) and performed the Flanker task in the concurrent task condition. Each tDCS stimulation session unfolded as follows: once participants were equipped with the stimulation headset, resting state EEG was recorded during 2 minutes eyes open (EO) and 2 minutes eyes closed (EC), followed by 20 minutes of tDCS stimulation. In the during stimulation concurrent task condition, the task started after 2.5 minutes of tDCS and ended 2.5 minutes before the end of the stimulation. In the non-concurrent task condition, participants were instructed to sit and relax with eyes opened.

After stimulation, a second resting state EEG was recorded (2 minutes EO, 2 minutes EC). Finally all participants performed the following cognitive tasks whilst their EEG was still being recorded: Flanker Task, N-Back Task and Continuous Performance Task (Figure 2).

Figure 2. T3 to T6 Trial Design. During each trial, 2 minutes eyes open and 2 minutes eyes closed resting state EEG are being recorded before and after the tDCS stimulation. After the intervention, participants perform each of the 3 behavioural tasks whilst their EEG is still being recorded.

Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation

Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) was applied using a Starstim 32 multi-channel stimulation device (Neuroelectronics - Barcelona, Spain). The montage consisted of 5 circular electrodes (3.14 cm²) filled with gel. The total stimulation current consisted of anodal 2mA during 20 minutes, with a 30 seconds of ramp up and down at the beginning and end of the stimulation (see Figure 3). The interested reader can find details on the DLPFC³⁴ and the IFG³⁵ montages in the referred works.

Figure 3. Stimulation Areas. Brain renders showing the component of the E-field normal to the cortical surface (E_n), positive/negative values indicate the into/out-of the cortical surface direction of the E_n , leading to an increase/decrease of excitability in cortical pyramidal cells. Group A of participants received stimulation in (A) left Dorsolateral Prefrontal cortex. Group B of participants received stimulation in (B) right Inferior frontal gyrus, the montage was optimized defining a target of Brodmann-areas 44, 45 and 47 on the right hemisphere.

EEG Recording

EEG Data was recorded using the same device used for the stimulation at a sampling rate of 500 Hz with 32 channels, following the 10-20 system: P8, T8, AF7, AF8, F8, F4, C4, P4, FC5, AF4, Fp2, Fp1, AF3, Fz, C6, Cz, C5, PO3, O1, Oz, O2, PO4, Pz, Fpz, FC6, P3, C3, F3, F7, FCz, T7, P7.

Behavioural Tasks

Behavioural tasks correspond to the Flanker Task, N-Back Task and Continuous Performance Test (Figure 4). These were programmed using Presentation® Software (Version 20.0, Neurobehavioural Systems, Inc., Berkeley, USA). Behavioural performance metrics were computed in R (version 3.6.1, R Core Team). The primary endpoints are the N-Back Accuracy for participants in Group A and the Flanker Accuracy for participants in Group B. For more details please see the associated experimental work³⁴.

Figure 4. Behavioural Tasks. Examples for Flanker Task (left), 2-Back Task (middle) and Continuous Performance Task (right).

Signal Processing and Feature Extraction

The EEG data analysed here corresponds to the 2-minutes resting state EEG in eyes closed condition recorded before the start of tDCS stimulation in each T3 to T6 trial for each participant. Data was first band pass filtered using a 1000 coefficients FIR filter with cut-off frequencies set at 2Hz and 45 Hz, demeaned and detrended. Frontal channels AF4, Fp2, Fp1 and AF3 were removed from further processing and analysis due to the presence of numerous eye movement related artifacts. High amplitude artifacts were removed using an amplitude threshold of 100 μ V. Finally, the data was re-referenced to electrode Cz, which was then excluded from further processing. The relative band power was computed in 4-second time-windows epochs with 50% overlap in bands delta (2-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-30 Hz) and gamma (30-45 Hz). The final relative band power values for each subject and session was taken as the median of the epochs. The EEG data pre-processing and analysis was done using custom scripts in Python 3.9.

Overview of the analytical approach

The Figure below (Figure 5) gives a schematic of the methods used in the core analytical approach of our work. Details of each step are given in the following Sections.

Figure 5. Schematic of Clustering and Wilcoxon Test Pipeline. EEG features are clustered and membership values are correlated with different behavioural metrics. If significance is reached (correlation p-value is less than 0.05), a Wilcoxon Test is done between the behavioural metric of that cluster and the rest of the points.

Unsupervised Clustering Analysis

We applied 2 different unsupervised clustering algorithms to the spectral features extracted from the EEG data: Spectral Clustering²⁸ (implementation from Python scikit-learn package³⁶) and Fuzzy C-Means³⁷ (implementation from Holt Skinner 2018³⁸). The definition of parameters for the clustering pipeline consisted of selecting the optimal number of clusters k ranging from 2 to 6, and the specific parameters for each algorithm (number of components n for Spectral Clustering and fuzzification parameter value m for Fuzzy C-Means). The parameters were chosen based on several internal validity measures and the visual inspection of the feature space in a 2-dimensional projection based on t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE). The used internal validity metrics are: Silhouette, Davies Bouldin Score (DB), Calinski-Harabasz (CH), Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) and Inertia (or Within-Cluster Sums of Squares), implemented in Python's Scikit-learn and SciPy packages. Good clustering is represented by low values of DB, Inertia and BIC, and high values of Silhouette and CH. We experienced a relative lack robustness of these metrics in our large dimensional space (5 different Band Power for each of the 27 EEG channels). Therefore we add a second criteria for the selection of parameters, namely the tSNE visualization, appropriate for maintaining local interactions and robust to the presence of outliers³⁹.

Cluster Membership definition and computation

For each participant we used 4 datasets (corresponding to each pre-stimulation EEG resting state recording in sessions T3 to T6). We thus obtained 4 different membership functions for each subject, which may present small variability due to the time between recording sessions, i.e. one week. As we are trying to establish a participant profile, we averaged the cluster membership functions of each subject over the 4 sessions. This average membership function is expected to be more robust than the individual session measures and to get rid of the temporal variability of subject profiles.

It is worth pointing out that the membership of each data sample to each of the clusters is defined in a real-valued domain. This was motivated to avoid losing information due to the binarization of the data. By defining memberships in a real-valued domain we are able to treat differently the points that are close to the cluster centres and the points that are close to the boundaries, i.e. since they present very different membership values to the cluster under consideration. This is expected to increase the robustness of the analysis pipeline, given the fact that early binarization thresholds largely influence final results.

Characterizing digital EEG phenotypes through Statistical Analysis

Correlation Analysis

After clustering, we correlated the membership function and the behavioural data of each participant using a Partial Spearman Correlation. This type of correlation allows to take into account spurious factors that may affect the EEG features. Hence the correlation was corrected for age, sex, IQ measured by the CFT 20-R and handedness measured with the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory (EHI). A correction to take into account the multiple comparisons was applied in order to avoid random significant values of the correlation measure. Hence the False Discovery Rate (FDR) was applied with one of the most common methods, namely the Benjamin and Hochberg step-up procedure (BH)⁴⁰.

The purpose of the correlational analysis is to label clusters, whose forming data samples are exclusively grouped upon their homogeneity, by associating the pre-tDCS EEG resting state characteristics to the behavioural response, and eventually to their condition of positive and negative responders. As behavioural response we have used the accuracy and reaction times in the Flanker task, N-Back and CPT tasks performed after the tDCS stimulation. Given we need a unique behavioural response to conduct the correlation, we have computed the difference in performance between the active and sham tDCS condition for each task and behavioural metric (accuracy and reaction time). This performance difference was computed independently for trials with a concurrent task during tDCS and trials without a concurrent task.

Since 4 experimental conditions exist, i.e. resulting from combining the 2 stimulation sites (Groups A/B) with the task concurrency (concurrent/non-concurrent task), for each clustering algorithm 4 correlations were computed. Hence we have correlated the performance difference of each experimental condition and the average membership to the cluster of each subject. The rationale for computing these 4 correlations is to identify the concrete protocols, i.e. stimulation site A/B and task concurrence, in which significant results are found and predict the response of the subjects. The objective is to study, for each protocol (concurrent/non-concurrent task during the stimulation), whether the active tDCS stimulation improves the behavioural performance with respect to performance achieved with the sham stimulation. If there is a significant correlation (results are considered statistically significant if the corrected correlation p-value is less than 0.05), we can establish a relationship between the digital EEG profile and the behavioural performance difference between the active and sham conditions. Positive responder clusters are detected for positive Accuracy correlations and negative RT correlations, since for the former it means that the active condition has a higher accuracy than the sham condition, whereas the opposite is expected for RT. On the other hand, negative responder clusters are defined by presenting a negative correlation with Accuracy measures and positive correlation with RT ones.

Wilcoxon Test

In those clusters labelled as including responders or non-responders, we aimed to statistically evaluate the response. If any of the 4 computations showed a significant correlation (positive or negative), then we analysed the difference in behavioural response for the members versus the non-members of the cluster. Thus a rank-sum Wilcoxon Test was calculated on the behavioural metrics within each cluster samples and the samples belonging to the remaining clusters. Benjamin and Hochberg step-up procedure (BH)⁴⁰ was used again to correct for multiple comparisons. In this part of the analysis we want to investigate if there are significant differences between the behavioural outcomes for each specific cluster, once the cluster has shown a correlation between the membership to that cluster and the corresponding behavioural metric. Hence, for each test in a cluster with a significant correlation, the significance of the difference in behavioural performance of that subject cluster members was evaluated with respect to the subjects belonging to the rest of the clusters. We illustrate this operation with an example: If a significant correlation is found for Cluster 1 in behavioural metric Accuracy Flanker – considering the membership values of all data-points to that specific Cluster 1 – then a Wilcoxon test is performed on the Flanker Accuracy Delta between the subjects that belong to Cluster 1 and the rest of the subjects. The objective of this step is to have an estimation of the improvement in the treatment response in case the clustering analysis is used for recruiting subjects in the clinical trial.

In this stage, since we were calculating the significant difference between the subject samples belonging to a cluster and the rest of the subject samples, we need to determine to which final cluster a subject belongs to. This was done through the arg max function over the membership values to the different clusters, i.e. determining the cluster with a highest membership value (e.g., if point X has a membership value of 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.1 for Clusters 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively, then it would belong to Cluster 3).

Results

Feature Space Analysis

We computed the relative band power in bands delta, theta, alpha, beta and gamma for each electrode resulting in a feature space of 135 components. After removal of artefacts and due to the absence of some trials or due to dropout subjects, 206 data-points were used. Figure 6 shows the feature space visualization with t-SNE in 2 dimensions, given by an optimal perplexity index value of 30³⁹. One interesting aspect here is to analyze how reproducible is the approach given that the 4 samples corresponding to each subject where acquired with a week in between. It can be seen that the samples of all 4 trials for each participant are very close to each other. Therefore we can state that the intra-subject variability is small enough to consider the feature representation as a robust one. Moreover, this robustness qualifies the average over the membership of the 4 trials in order to obtain a unique membership per subject for the correlation analysis.

Clustering Results

We implemented the different clustering algorithms to establish homogeneous subgroups among subjects based on their resting-state EEG spectral features before intervention. The evolution of the validity measures over the different parameters do not offer a clear criterion for parameter selection. We believe this may be due to the high dimensionality of the feature space, i.e. the “curse of dimensionality”⁴¹, which seem not clearly tackled by the most common validity measures. Nevertheless, we observe some singular points in the evolution of the selected validity measures over clustering parameters (see Figure 7 B). Given the shortcoming of the validity measures to offer a clear objective criteria for parameter selection, we have taken into account an additional qualitative evaluation criteria based on the visualization of the t-SNE projection of the clustered feature space. Figure 7 A shows well separated and clear cluster clouds. For the Spectral Clustering, a number of components n equal to the number of centres was used, as it generally corresponds to the default parameter. This gives better results than a number of components n equal to 100 applied as an example for extreme values, and gives similar results to smaller values such as 2, 6 and 8. For FCM the chosen parameter was a fuzzification parameter m of 1.7 since it differs sufficiently from 1 (so as to be more dissimilar to K-means) and presenting optimal values for the validity metrics and visualization in the feature space.

Figure 6. Feature Space. Visualization of EEG data-points with t-SNE in 2 dimensions. Each point corresponds to a specific trial for each participant, the features of each data-point are the RBP in each channel.

Concretely we can observe some singular points, i.e. “elbows”, for $k = 4$ clusters for the Spectral Clustering algorithm that correspond to the optimal values. For the case of FCM algorithm it is optimal in $k = 5$. In order to have the largest amount of data-points in each cluster cloud, and since it shows clearly defined clusters in the visualization from both algorithms, we eventually defined the number of cluster centres as $k = 4$. Since the clustering output visualized in the feature space shows similar results for both algorithms, a possible hypothesis for the differences in point cluster assignment between Spectral and FCM is the difference in the way the membership functions are computed in each algorithm (FCM results for $k = 4$ can be

found in Supplementary Information for the sake of comparison). Given the similarity of the clustering results the results in the following sections are shown for the Spectral Clustering.

Figure 7. Clustering Results for Spectral Clustering. The left plot shows the feature Space, colourcode represents each cluster. From all data-points, 42,7% lie in Cluster 1, 7,3% in Cluster 2, 18,4% in Cluster 3 and 31,6% in Cluster 4. The right plots show the evolution of the internal validity metrics Silhouette and Davies Bouldin when changing the number of centres. An elbow at $k=4$ can be seen.

Clustering Validation

The robustness of the parameter search in the clustering methodology was validated through a M-fold-out using 80% of the data for parameter search. The chosen algorithms with their corresponding parameters (fuzzification parameter m of 1.7 for Fuzzy c-Means and number of components n equal to number of centres for Spectral Clustering) and number of centres k were applied to a subset of the data-points and then tested in the remaining points, checking whether the clusters assigned to the test set generalize to the ones obtained on the training set. This was done by first clustering the train data samples and plotting them in the feature space. The remaining test data samples labels were then assigned according to their nearest distance to the final centre previously obtained.

The validation is successful given the visual overlap between the clusters assigned to the test set, which are not used in the parameter search (see Figure 6 A in Supplementary Information). Moreover, the internal validity metrics follow the same trend in both data subsets (see Figure 6 B in Supplementary Information).

Digital Electroencephalography Phenotypes

In order to characterize each of the clusters in terms of the associated digital EEG profiles, the prototypes generated for each cluster of each algorithm were used. The electrophysiological profiles are set up as a combination of a representation in the frequency and spatial domains. First, the power spectrum for each cluster prototype is plotted (Figure 8) using the mean of occipital and parietal electrodes (i.e. O1, O2, Oz, P8, P4, P3, P7, PO3, PO4, Pz). Taking the alpha peak during eyes closed as reference, differences can be observed between the different clusters. These can be further analyzed on hand of the scalp power distributions in the spatial domain.

Topoplots are used for the representation of prototypes in the spatial domain (Figure 9). They are visualized calculating the mean of the relative band power of all of the data-points belonging to each cluster.

Cluster 1 presents the neurotypical PSD and scalp power distribution for eyes closed, with alpha power localized over posterior regions. This could be observed as well in the PSDs (see Figure 8). Cluster 2 presents a very clear slowing in both the PSD and the topoplots, from the alpha band towards the theta band. Cluster 3 presents low amplitude in 10 Hz and large amplitudes at higher powers in the PSD. Cluster 4 presents the largest amplitude in 10 Hz and a peak in 20 Hz in the PSD, and the difference between frontal and parietal areas for the alpha band in the topoplot is smaller compared to the rest of the clusters. As a remark, Cluster 1 topographical map of activation is the most similar to the ones of the overall study population (see Figure 10).

Figure 8. Power Spectrum Density of each Cluster for Spectral Clustering Results.

Figure 9. Power Spectrum Plot of each Cluster for Spectral Algorithm Results.

Figure 10. Overall Population Topoplot.

Figure 11. Example of significant positive responder group for Spectral Clustering (Cluster 2), with rIFG stimulation with no concurrent task, measured with N-Back Accuracy. (A) Correlation between cluster membership of pre treatment EEG spectral features of all participants and N-Back Accuracy at the end of the trials. Best-fit line showing least square polynomial fit. (B) Wilcoxon Test between N-Back Accuracy of Cluster 2 Spectral members, and the members of the rest of the Clusters. The raw data is visualized as points as well as the probability density, and key summary statistics in the boxplot (median, mean, and confidence intervals).

Behavioural Correlational Analysis

We applied the described correlation analysis between participants' membership to each cluster and the post-tDCS behavioural results of Accuracy and RT for the Flanker, N-Back and CPT tasks. Due to the low variability in the baseline EEG spectral activity of each participant (Figure 6), the average of the membership function over all trials of each participant was computed as aforementioned. Eleven subjects were excluded due to incorrect randomization and/or dropouts during the trials, and behavioural outliers are removed for each metric using a threshold of ± 2.5 standard deviations. The correlational analysis can be used to label the clusters in terms of their positive or negative responding nature. A specific example of the positive response is that of cluster 2, whose members are positive responding to the rIFG stimulation with non-concurrent task (see Figure 11). Negative responses are detected by the correlational analysis as well (see Figure 5 A in Supplementary Information).

The following matrices (Figure 12) show the strength of the partial Spearman correlation and the range of the p-val when significant (* - 10%, ** - 5% and *** - 1%) after correction for multiple comparison with FDR (24 corrections for Group B, 20 corrections for Group A). These matrices summarize the findings achieved by the correlational analysis.

Figure 12. Correlation Results for Spectral Clustering. Each matrix row corresponds to a specific behavioural task endpoint, and each matrix column corresponds to a particular treatment protocol. The colourbar represents the sign of the correlation (positive or negative) and p-values are written in the significant cells. For Group B, 24 corrections are done; for Group A, 20 corrections are applied.

Cluster vs Non-Cluster Differences

We compute the rank-sum Wilcoxon test only in clusters with significant correlation results. Responder clusters (positive or negative) are analyzed with respect to the difference to non-responder ones. Responding clusters are confirmed by giving significant differences in this test as well (see Figure 11 for an example of a positive responder cluster and Figure 5 B in Supplementary Information for a negative one). Corrected results for multiple comparisons for the Wilcoxon analysis, as well as number of corrections, are presented in Table 1.

The robustness of the correlational analysis was tested iterating 1000 different percentages of the data set (specifically 80%, 60% and 40%). We find a trend for the coefficients and p-values of both correlations and Wilcoxon tests. Overall, the sets have same direction of correlation as the whole dataset, and the strength goes diminishing in the order 80%-60%-40%. With respect to the correlation p-value, it is almost always significant (correlation p-value is less than 0.05) for the 80% dataset. In the 60% dataset it is generally non-significant although very close to the boundary (correlation p-value near 0.05) and for the 40% it is never significant. In both cases, the standard deviation increases when the percentage of data-points decreases. These takeaways have similar trends for the analysis using Wilcoxon test. For the case of the distance to the original fit line (with the 100% of data-points), the mean is very similar in all percentages of the dataset, whereas the standard deviation increases for decreasing percentages. Overall, results show that our correlation method is robust and that the sample size used is the minimum required for obtaining these results.

Since previous work state that subjects who better respond to treatment correspond to those who start in worse conditions⁴²⁻⁴⁴, an extra analysis was done in order to discard the differential response in terms of this factor. Hence we further studied whether there is a relationship between baseline behavioural measures (at T3) and treatment response. The following Figure 13 shows the behavioural response for the baseline (T3) of the main endpoints (Flanker Accuracy and N-Back Accuracy) as well as for the RT of those tasks. No cluster structure can be seen on the behavioural metric at baseline. Therefore we can state that the cluster structure is solely due to homogeneous digital electrophysiological profiles and not at differential baseline response to the tasks.

Cluster	Group A, Concurrent	Group A, Non-concurrent	Group B, Concurrent	Group B, Non-concurrent
1			Flanker Accuracy (-, 0.0150)	
2				N-Back Accuracy (+, 0.0345)
3			Flanker RT (+, 0.0150)	Flanker RT (-, 0.0433)
4			Flanker RT (-, 0.0402)	Flanker RT (+, 0.0345)

Table 1. Spectral Significant Responders. These results correspond to significant correlations and significant Wilcoxon tests. In parenthesis are: (1) type of response (positive or negative), (2) Wilcoxon p-values. There are significant correlations only in Group B, therefore for Wilcoxon Test 4 corrections are done for Non-concurrent Group and 3 for Concurrent Group. Stimulation protocol Group B (rIFG), offline mode (non-concurrent task) presents positive response in Clusters 2 and 4 measured with N-Back Accuracy and Flanker RT respectively, and negative response in Cluster 3 assessed with Flanker RT. Stimulation protocol B (rIFG), active mode (with Flanker concurrent task) presents negative response in Clusters 1 and 4 measured with Flanker Accuracy and Flanker RT respectively, and positive response in Cluster 3 assessed with Flanker RT.

Figure 13. Baseline behavioural tasks distinguished by Spectral Algorithm Clustering for (A) Accuracy and (B) Reaction Time.

Discussion

Our work provides a novel approach to study the effects of multichannel anodal tDCS treatment in healthy children and adolescents with different specific brain profiles. This is of interest given the limitations of existent treatments in paediatric clinical populations, e.g. ADHD and ASD for which new treatments with no side effects⁴⁵ are being developed. The proposed unsupervised learning approach constitutes a good alternative to address the usage of one-model-fit-all approaches based on supervised learning, whose problems to predict behavioural response have been recently analyzed⁴⁶. Furthermore the prognostic value of such approaches can be exploited in the context of the development of reliable and well-defined personalized protocols. Given that significant positive response to treatment is not always guaranteed, the proposed subject stratification approach can be of enormous value for the cost-effective development of new treatments.

By grouping experimental subjects in those with typical versus non-typical digital EEG profiles, a differentiated response can be found in subjects with a non-typical electrophysiological profile. EEG profiles (summarized in Figure 14) are characterized only by homogeneous resting-state EEG spectral features and not by behavioural response to tasks before each intervention. This confirms our hypothesis that the electrophysiological profile can be used as a proxy of different biophysical characteristics of the brain in experimental subjects. These characteristics are almost identical at 4 different measurement time points as shown in the intra-subject variability analysis. Therefore we can state that the electrophysiological profiles are subject specific and do not correspond to a difference in brain state. This is an important question given that brain state is known to influence as well the response to Non Invasive Brain Stimulation (NIBS)⁴⁷. We propose the usage of the stratified electrophysiological responses as shown herein as digital EEG phenotypes for the characterization of tDCS response.

It can be observed that Group B (rIFG stimulation) is the only one with responders (positive and negative), and Group A does not have any significant correlations supported with significant Wilcoxon-test results. This suggests an advantage in terms of task performance in stimulating the rIFG over the more traditional approach of IDLPFC stimulation even when participant stratification is applied. In almost all groups of participants, the behavioural task showing changes is the Flanker task when the applied stimulation montage targets augmenting activity of the rIFG. This result is consistent with current understanding of the role of the rIFG, associated with response inhibition and behavioural control^{48,49}.

Future work could be done in order to establish a relationship between the electrophysiological profiles and functional outcomes. A hypothesis would be based on the transfer stimulation effects from stimulated WM network involved in the Flanker task to the WM network components involved in N-Back task^{34,50-52}, and the response dependency to the brain's stage of development since for example Clusters 3 and 4 have different neurophysiological characteristics and show opposite results^{34,53}.

In summary, we can state that the effect of brain stimulation (and its parameters including location and presence/absence of concurrent task during the protocol), measured by different behavioural measures, depends on the individual digital EEG phenotype of the subjects undergoing the stimulation intervention. Such a digital phenotype can be derived by applying the developed clustering approach. The robustness of the overall developed methodology was validated in 3 independent tests. First, the feature space of all participants was visualized showing that the features of all trials of pre-treatment EEG for each subject lie close to each other. Therefore their baseline neurophysiological activity was similar over the different trials. Second, the k-fold-out methodology applied to the clustering pipeline demonstrates the robustness of the clustering algorithms in our specific dataset. This validation let us ensure to a certain extent the generalization capability of the clustering for generating similar digital EEG phenotypes on unseen data. Finally, the M-fold-out methodology applied to the correlational and wilcoxon test analysis shows a decreasing trend with decreasing sizes of our dataset. Moreover it shows also that the behavioural response differences are robust enough to resist a reduction of 20% in the data set sample size.

Some limitations arise from the fact that the dataset is relatively small compared to the large amount of features analysed, resulting in a very high dimensional space for the employed clustering validity measures. This hinders to a certain extent the full automation of the methodology. In order to reduce the feature space dimensionality, Principal Feature Analysis⁵⁴, permutation analysis²⁰ and other feature selection algorithms^{55,56} could be explored to reduce the number of features. However the application of such approaches would decrease the explainability of the resulting methodology, i.e. digital phenotypes could not be given in form of a complete electrophysiological characterization.

Figure 14. Summary of EEG Prototypes. Topoplots and PSD for Clusters that present a significant response in Spectral Algorithm. Cluster 1 (blue PSD) has a negative response to rIFG stimulation with Flanker concurrent task, measured with Flanker Accuracy. Cluster 2 (orange PSD) has a positive response to rIFG stimulation with no concurrent task, measured with N-Back Accuracy. Cluster 3 (green PSD) has a positive response to rIFG stimulation with Flanker concurrent task, measured with Flanker RT; and a negative response to rIFG stimulation with no concurrent task, measured with Flanker RT. Cluster 4 (red PSD) has a positive response to rIFG stimulation with no concurrent task, measured with Flanker RT; and a negative response to rIFG stimulation with Flanker concurrent task, measured with Flanker RT.

Conclusions

The advanced clustering methodology we developed shows promising results in the context of broad and heterogeneous EEG signals⁵⁷. Moreover the use of unsupervised learning approaches allows to obtain an actual data-driven stratification, since the learning procedure is freely run without the constraints imposed by the ground truth. This is an important factor given the large misdiagnosis rates in the target diseases^{58,59}, especially important in ADHD⁵⁹. In case of having used a supervised approach, a false ground truth might have driven the class structure wrongly and hinder the accuracy of the stratification.

Stimulation brain target areas studied were IDLPFC and rIFG, paired or not with concurrent tasks N-Back and Flanker Tasks respectively. Effectiveness of the treatment was assessed by different behavioural measures, in particular RT and Accuracy of the aforementioned tasks. The digital phenotypes obtained from pre-treatment EEG, as computed by the clustering procedure described throughout the work, can be then used to predict the response of individuals to particular stimulation protocols. We have successfully developed a procedure for labelling clusters in terms of their behavioural response in different tasks. Hence a rank-sum Wilcoxon test is successfully applied for validation and consistency of results.

Interestingly, positive responder groups correspond to participants with a non-typical brain profile, presenting either a slowing of the EEG or a spread of increased alpha rhythm over frontal areas. This finding is extremely interesting from a neurophysiological point of view. However, we focus in this communication on the novelty of the methodology of our work. A larger cohort of participants would be needed for confirming the clinical utility of the proposed approach.

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Data Availability Statement

Due to ethical restriction, the data from this study will not be able to be accessible from public domain. The data are available upon request. Vera Moliadze (STIPED consortium), Institute of Medical Psychology and Medical Sociology, University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein, Kiel University, Kiel, Germany (moliadze@med-psych.uni-kiel.de).

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Author contributions statement

Experimental Study concept and design: M.Sin., K.K., V.M. Conduction of experiment and Data collection: M.S., V.M. Methodology concept: A.S.F. Analysis: P.D., A.S.F., E.K., C.B. Interpretation of results: P.D., A.S.F., E.K., C.B. Analysis supervision: A.S.F., E.K., C.B. Drafting of the manuscript: P.D., A.S.F., E.K., C.B. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Additional information

Neuroelectrics is the company that manufactures the Starstim devices used for stimulation and recording of EEG analysed in this work. We, all authors, declare there are no conflict of interests with this publication and we have all approved this final version.